

TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING MOVING GAMES TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. The article examines the pedagogical foundations of teaching moving games to primary school students in the system of physical education. Particular attention is paid to the development of an effective teaching technology aimed at improving physical qualities, increasing motivation for physical activity, and forming social and communicative skills among younger schoolchildren. Moving games are considered as an important pedagogical tool for strengthening health, developing coordination, agility, speed, endurance, and fostering discipline and teamwork. The study was conducted in general secondary schools with the participation of 3rd-4th grade students. During the pedagogical experiment, the effectiveness of a specially developed methodology based on systematic game organization, age characteristics, differentiated tasks, and interactive teaching methods was evaluated. The obtained results demonstrated a significant increase in students' physical preparedness, activity during lessons, emotional involvement, and stable interest in physical education classes. It was established that the use of modern teaching technology for moving games contributes to improving the educational process and increasing the effectiveness of physical education in primary school.

Keywords: moving games, primary school students, physical education, teaching technology, pedagogical experiment, physical preparedness, motivation, game methods, motor activity, primary education

Introduction. In the modern educational system, special attention is paid to preserving and strengthening children's health, forming a healthy lifestyle, and developing stable motivation for regular physical activity [3, 4]. The issue of improving physical education in primary school has become especially relevant in the context of increasing sedentary behavior among children, the growing influence of digital technologies, and the reduction of natural motor activity in everyday life. Researchers emphasize that primary school age is the most sensitive period for the development of fundamental motor skills, coordination abilities, speed, agility, endurance, and positive attitudes toward physical culture and sports [1, 2, 4].

According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization, children of primary school age should engage in moderate to vigorous physical activity for at least 60 minutes daily, which is essential for their healthy physical, emotional, and cognitive development. However, many studies indicate that the actual level of physical activity among schoolchildren remains insufficient, which negatively affects both their physical preparedness and academic performance [5, 7].

Moving games occupy a special place in the system of physical education for younger schoolchildren [6]. They are considered not only as a means of physical development but also as an effective pedagogical instrument for the formation of discipline, initiative, independence, teamwork skills, communication culture, and emotional stability. Through игровая activity, children perceive educational material more naturally, show greater emotional involvement, and actively participate in collective interaction. Unlike traditional repetitive exercises, moving games create a positive emotional background and reduce psychological tension during physical education lessons [9, 10].

Many scholars have studied the pedagogical significance of moving games. L.P. Matveev emphasized that game methods in physical education significantly improve children's motor preparedness and stimulate sustainable interest in physical exercise. V.K. Balsevich noted that systematic use of active games contributes to the harmonious development of personality and strengthens adaptive mechanisms of the child's organism. N.G. Ozolin considered moving games as one of the most effective means of developing speed-strength qualities and coordination abilities in schoolchildren.

In the works of P.F. Lesgaft, the educational value of physical exercises and games was closely connected with the development of willpower, discipline, and moral qualities. Modern researchers such as V.I. Lyakh and B.A. Ashmarin also underline that moving games are an important mechanism for developing social adaptation and self-regulation skills in children of младшего школьного возраста.

In recent years, the concept of student-centered and differentiated teaching has become increasingly important. This approach requires the selection of moving games according to age characteristics, physical preparedness, psychological comfort, and individual educational needs of students. The effectiveness of physical education largely depends on how correctly the teacher organizes the educational environment, distributes physical loads, motivates students, and integrates educational and health-improving tasks within the lesson structure [7].

At the same time, traditional methods of conducting physical education lessons do not always ensure sufficient involvement of students and effective development of motor qualities. In many schools, moving games are used unsystematically, without methodological planning and without considering pedagogical objectives. This reduces their educational potential and limits the formation of stable motivation toward physical education.

Therefore, the improvement of teaching technology for moving games based on modern pedagogical approaches, age characteristics, differentiated instruction, and motivational strategies becomes a necessary condition for increasing the effectiveness of physical education in primary school. The use of specially developed pedagogical technologies allows not only improving students' physical preparedness but also forming positive attitudes toward health-preserving behavior and lifelong physical activity.

The relevance of the present study is determined by the need to improve the methodology of teaching moving games in primary school physical education lessons in order to enhance the quality of educational outcomes, strengthen students' health, and ensure the harmonious development of the child's personality.

The purpose of the study is to determine the effectiveness of the technology of teaching moving games to primary school students under the conditions of general secondary education.

Materials and Methods. The study was conducted during the 2025-2026 academic year in 4 general secondary schools of Surkhandarya region. The participants included 120 students of grades 3-4 and 8 physical education teachers.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following research methods were used:

- analysis of scientific and methodological literature;
- pedagogical observation;
- testing of physical preparedness;
- questionnaires for students and teachers;
- pedagogical experiment;
- comparative analysis;
- methods of mathematical statistics.

The students were divided into two groups:

- control group (n = 60) - traditional teaching of moving games;
- experimental group (n = 60) - teaching based on the developed technology of moving games.

The experimental methodology included:

- systematic use of age-appropriate moving games;
- differentiated physical tasks;
- team and competitive game methods;
- interactive forms of physical activity;
- motivational encouragement;
- integration of educational and health-improving tasks.

The experiment lasted for 5 months. The following indicators were assessed:

- speed and agility;
- coordination abilities;
- endurance;
- motivation for physical education;
- active participation in lessons.

Results. The results of the pedagogical experiment showed significant positive changes in the experimental group compared to the control group.

Table 1

Indicators of the effectiveness of teaching moving games to primary school students (%)

Indicators	Control Group (Before)	Control Group (After)	Experimental Group (Before)	Experimental Group (After)
High level of speed and agility	28.4	34.1	27.9	59.3
Developed coordination abilities	26.7	31.8	27.1	57.6
High endurance level	24.9	29.5	25.3	53.8
High motivation for physical education	33.2	38.4	32.6	68.1
Active participation in lessons	30.5	36.0	31.4	71.2

The most significant increase was observed in the indicator of active participation in lessons, where the experimental group improved from 31.4% to 71.2%, while the control group showed only moderate growth.

Motivation for physical education also increased considerably, indicating that students became more emotionally involved and interested in participating in physical activities through game-based learning.

Improvements in coordination, agility, and endurance confirmed that systematic use of moving games positively affects the comprehensive physical development of younger schoolchildren.

The results demonstrate that the developed teaching technology creates favorable pedagogical conditions for increasing lesson effectiveness and improving the quality of physical education in primary school.

Discussion. The obtained results confirm the effectiveness of using moving games as an important pedagogical technology in primary school physical education. Modern studies show that game-based learning significantly improves both physical preparedness and psychological comfort of children during lessons.

Moving games create a natural educational environment where physical activity is combined with emotional involvement, social adaptation, and cognitive development. Children perceive game tasks more positively than traditional repetitive exercises, which increases lesson productivity and educational motivation.

The developed methodology demonstrated that systematic planning of moving games according to age characteristics and pedagogical goals ensures higher educational outcomes. Particularly important is the use of differentiated tasks that allow each child to participate successfully regardless of their initial physical preparedness.

The study also showed that teacher readiness and methodological competence are key factors in the successful implementation of moving game technologies. Without proper pedagogical organization, the educational potential of games may be significantly reduced.

Therefore, improving teacher training and updating methodological support remain important directions for further development.

Conclusion. The technology of teaching moving games to primary school students is an effective pedagogical tool for improving the quality of physical education.

The use of a systematic game-based approach contributes to:

- improving physical preparedness;
- developing speed, agility, coordination, and endurance;
- increasing motivation for physical education;
- strengthening social interaction skills;
- forming positive attitudes toward a healthy lifestyle.

The results of the study confirm the expediency of the widespread introduction of modern moving game technologies into the educational process of primary school physical education.

Further research prospects are associated with the development of digital game technologies and adaptive methods for inclusive physical education in primary school.

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